

Prevalence, Nature and Causes of Domestic Violence in Ekiti State

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Abstract:

The study examined prevalence, nature and causes of domestic violence in Ekiti State. This study adopted descriptive cross sectional survey research design. It employed mixed methods which are qualitative and quantitative strands to gather information from a representative sample of the population under study. The target population was women from five selected wards in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area, Ekiti State. The sample size for this study was calculated using Fischer's formula, this was considered appropriate because of the large population. Adjustment for a 10% rate of non-responses and invalid responses yielded a final sample size of 246. The research instrument used in collecting data for this study was a semi-structured questionnaire. The research instrument used in collecting data for the qualitative study was an in-depth interview guide. Validity of the instrument was based on both face and content validity. To ensure the reliability of the instruments, Cronbach alpha method was employed to determine the internal consistency which yielded a reliability value of 0.85. Quantitative data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics while the qualitative data were transcribed and a full description of all verbal and non-verbal statements were generated. The study revealed that the proportion of domestic violence in Ekiti State was high while there was relationship between socio-economic status and level of domestic violence. Also type of family was related with the level of domestic violence. However, there was no relationship between educational level and level of domestic violence. It was recommended among others that public awareness

EASIJ

Accepted 25 September 2021
Published 30 September 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6012581

should be created in social gatherings like churches, mosque, seminars, symposium and social media about domestic violence.

Keywords: Prevalence, Nature, Causes, Domestic Violence,

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Introduction

Violence against women perpetrated by an intimate partner is an important public health issue. Males are the most prevalent perpetrators of violence against women, despite the fact that women can be aggressive in relationships with men (Oche & Adamu, 2020). According to WHO, (2017), physical, emotional or sexual, as well as controlling behavior, are all signs of domestic violence, which can occur in the workplace, school, or community. The most common kind of violence is believed to be domestic violence. Domestic violence jeopardizes the economic stability of nation, families and people, by lowering productivity, increasing physical and psychological stress, stigmatizing victims, and limiting access to education (USAID, 2016). Domestic violence according to Alebiosu (2019) is addressed as intimate partner violence (IPV), domestic abuse or relationship abuse could be described as a pattern of behavior used by one partner in an intimated relationship. Hoak (2016) posited that domestic violence is now commonly defined to include all acts of physical, sexual, psychological or economic violence that may be committed against women by a family member or intimate partner.

Alokan (2014) affirmed that domestic violence is not limited to physical violence; it can mean endangerment, criminal coercion and kidnaping, unlawful imprisonment, trespassing, harassment and stalking. The United State office of violence against women (OVM) asserted that domestic violence can happen to anyone regardless of race, age, sexual orientation, religion or genders and can take many forms, including physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional, economic and psychological abuse (Office of Violence Against Women ,2017).

According to Alebiosu (2019), prevalence of domestic violence in Nigeria ranges from 31 to 61% for psychological /emotional violence, and 7 to 31% for physical violence. South Africa is said to have the highest statistics of domestic violence (The integrated Regional Network [IRIN], 2018). In multi-country study conducted in 10 different countries, a rate ranging from 18.5 to 75.8% was reported. Domestic violence by an intimate partner alone had a rate of 15.5% to 70.9% while violence by non-partners ranged between 5.1 to 64.6% (Alebiosu, 2019). Domestic violence ranging from 4 to 29 percent is prevalent among women in developing nations. Domestic violence among women in Nigeria varies by region with south-south region having the highest frequency of about 9% and north-central (7%) regions has the least (NDHS, 2018). Domestic violence was highlighted as a high priority problem by the Pan American Health Organization in their resolution in 2000, and it was declared a public health priority by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2015 (Oluremi, 2016).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 18 to 67 percent of women in under developed nations face a multitude of risk factors that affect them from getting pregnant as they are being, mentally, and physically abused. According to Bakare et. al (2018), prevalence of domestic violence in Ekiti State was 21%. Another study revealed that 89.2% experienced medium physical abuse during pregnancy. This result demonstrates the negative effects of domestic violence on mother-infant emotional attachment. In addition, husbands who disapproved of their wives' pregnancy were more likely to physically and verbally attack/abuse their wives (Marcus & Braaf, 2017).

Variety of findings about what causes of domestic violence have been reported. Jealousy has resulted to many reported cases of domestic violence against women most especially when a spouse is suspected of being unfaithful or plans to leave the relationship. Stress does not necessarily lead to violence, but it is one of the ways that people respond to it (Bhuiya, 2016). Due to heightened stress and arguments about financial and other issues, poor couples are more likely to encounter domestic violence. Stress may be increased when a person is living in a family situation, with increased pressures. In most times, violence is transferred from one generation to another generation in a cyclical manner. Poverty stress, feelings of inadequacy or low self-esteem, unresolved childhood conflicts, personality disorders, hatred toward women (misogyny) and animosity, societal cultural influences and genetic tendencies have all been linked to abusers' attempts to dominate (Alebiosu, 2019).

The prevalence of domestic violence among women has remained high and become a public health concern in recent times. Domestic violence affects both male and female, Nigeria happens to be one of the countries with the highest prevalence of domestic violence. Although domestic violence is common in Ekiti but a significant proportion remained unreported and victims are still suffering in silence which may be due to poor enforcement and implementation of policies, lack of political will, poor funding of programs related to violence. There have been reports of cases of husbands battering, maiming and killing of wives in the media. The case of Ekiti State was not an exception as it was reported that a 42year old man beats his wife to death for denying him sex at Erio Ekiti (Punch, 2016). At Ikole-Ekiti, a woman pleaded with the customary court to dissolve her marriage with her husband as a result of neglect, lack of care and constant beating for not bearing a male child.

In view of the above, the study examined prevalence, nature and causes of domestic violence in Ekiti State. The study specifically examined:

1. the nature of domestic violence experienced by women in Ekiti State;
2. the factors responsible for domestic violence against women in Ekiti State;
3. the prevalence of domestic violence in Ekiti State; and

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised in this study

Quantitative

1. What is the nature of domestic violence experienced by women in Ekiti State?
2. What are the factors responsible for domestic violence against women in Ekiti State?

Qualitative

1. What is the prevalence of domestic violence in Ekiti State?
2. What are the factors responsible for domestic violence against women in Ekiti State?

Research Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant association between socio-economic status and level of domestic violence

Ho2: There is no significant association between participant's level of education and level of domestic violence

Ho3: There is no significant association between participant's type of family and level of domestic violence

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive cross sectional survey research design. It employed mixed methods which are qualitative and quantitative strands to gather information from a representative sample of the population under study. The target population was women from five selected wards (Dallimore, Idolofin, Basiri, Igirigiri, and Oke ila) in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area, Ekiti State. According to National demographic health survey, 2016, total numbers of women in Ado LGA, Ekiti State was 142,152. The sample size for this study was calculated using Fischer's formula, this was considered appropriate because of the large population. Adjustment for a 10% rate of non-responses and invalid responses yielded a final sample size of 246. Multistage sampling procedure was employed in the selection of sample for this study in order to capture adequate participants for the study.

The research instrument used in collecting data for this study was a semi-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of three sections; section A is socio- demographic data i.e. age, marital status, occupation, socio- economic status, level of education, tribe and religion. Section B assessed the Nature of domestic violence experienced while section C was designed to elicit factors responsible for domestic violence. The research instrument used in collecting data for the qualitative study was an in-depth interview guide. Researchers were present to document the comments. Interview guide contains two sections; A and B: Section A- socio-demographic characteristics of the participants i.e age, marital status, occupation, socio-economic status, level of education and religion. Section B- interview questions

Validity of the instrument was based on both face and content validity. The instrument was validated by experts of Tests and Measurement and Nursing Science. To ensure the reliability of the instruments, Cronbach alpha method was employed to determine the internal consistency which yielded a reliability value of 0.85. Quantitative data were collected through the use of researcher's administered questionnaire. The questionnaires consist of both open and close ended questions. Two hundred and forty-six (246) questionnaires were given out for the collection of information required. Qualitative data were collected through the use of in depth interview. 19 participants took part in the interview undertaken in 5 selected wards in Ado Local Government, Ekiti State. The interview was semi- structured and conducted by the researcher and her assistants face to face with women in their places of residence. Each session of the Interview usually lasted for 35-40minutes for a period of one month. Majority of the participants were given incentives in cash and gift items after each interview session.

Quantitative data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics while the qualitative data were transcribed and a full description of all verbal and non-verbal statements were generated. NVivo version 11 thematic approach was used to analyze responses to interview questions, by coding and categorizing collected data.

Results

Those who participated in this study were all women who had experienced/were experiencing domestic violence in their homes in Igirigiri, Idolofin, Okeila, Basiri and Ajebandele in Ado Local Government, Ekiti State. The table below presents socio-demographic variables of the study participants. Those between ages 30 and 39 years participated 41.1%, followed by those between ages 40 – 49 years constituted 63(25.6%), while the teenagers (18-19 years) constituted least number of participants. Two hundred

and eight (84.6%) of the participants were married, while 6 (2.4%) were singles. The participants were mostly those who have tertiary level of education who constituted 49.2% followed by those who have secondary school level of education (30.9%); 18(7.3%) participants had no formal education while the rest had primary level education. The domiciling religion was Christianity having a participatory percentage of 56.5%; 86 (35.5%) were Muslims while the rest were traditional worshippers. Monogamy family setting was practiced by 149(60.6%) participants followed by polygamy which was practice by 73 (29.7%) participants while the rest practiced extended family settings. Those from the Yoruba tribe were 163(66.3%) while the Fulani's had the least number of participants. Fifty-nine (24.0%) were public servants, 87(35.4%) were traders and 47 (19.1%) were full house wife

Table 1: Participants socio-demographic variable (N = 246)

Socio-demographic variables	Frequency	Percent	Mean \pm SD
Age range			
18-19	2	0.8	38 \pm 9.0
20-29	45	18.3	
30-39	101	41.1	
40-49	63	25.6	
50 above	35	14.2	
Marital status			
Single	6	2.4	
Married	208	84.6	
Divorced	17	6.9	
Widow	15	6.1	
Socio-economic status			
High	46	18.7	
Average	148	60.2	
Low	52	21.1	
Level of education			
Uneducated	18	7.3	
Primary	31	12.6	
Secondary	76	30.9	
Tertiary	121	49.2	
Religion			
Christian	139	56.5	
Muslim	86	35.0	
Traditionalist	21	8.5	
Type of family			

Monogamy	149	60.6	
Polygamy	73	29.7	
Extended	24	9.8	
Tribe			
Hausa	37	15.0	
Yoruba	163	66.3	
Igbo	31	12.6	
Fulani	15	6.1	
Occupation			
Public servant	59	24.0	
Contractor	24	9.8	
Trader	87	35.4	
Artisan	26	10.6	
Full house wife	47	19.1	
Applicants	3	1.2	

Research Question 1: What is the nature of domestic violence experienced by women in Ekiti State?

The table below presents the result of domestic violence women experienced from their husband. From findings, 100 (40.7%) women indicated that that they were always treated like a servant and that they also were not involved in decision making, 40 (16.3%) were always attacked with knives and other weapons, 107 (43.5%) women were sexually starved for weeks while 62 (25.2%) women were forcefully engaged in un-natural sexually practice by their spouse, 74 (30.1%) were either often or always beaten on other body parts and also punched with fist and some other objects (table 2)

Table 2: Nature of domestic violence experienced by participants (N = 246)

List of what you have suffered or experienced	Yes		No	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
I am always treated like a servant by my spouse	100	40.7	146	59.3
He insulted me in front of others	91	37.0	155	63.0
He slapped me times without number	71	28.9	175	71.1
I am not allow to partake in decision-making in the home	100	40.7	146	59.3
Always attacked me with knife or some other weapons	40	16.3	206	83.7
He beats me on other body parts	74	30.1	172	69.9
Twisted my arm/pulled my hair	41	16.7	205	83.3
Pushed/shook me or threw something at me	68	27.6	178	72.4

Punched me with fist or some object	74	30.1	171	69.5
Ignored me purposely, by not having sexual intercourse with me for weeks	107	43.5	139	56.5
Kicked me/dragged me often	67	27.2	179	72.8
Had sexual intercourse with me forcibly, when I was not interested	78	31.7	168	68.3
I'm always forced to engage in un-natural sexual practices, which I hated	62	25.2	184	74.8
He was unfaithful to me/had extra-marital relationships	93	37.8	153	62.2

Research Question 2: What are the factors responsible for domestic violence against women in Ekiti State?

In reference to the results from table 3 below, one of the most responsible factors for domestic violence was the in-laws interference in family issues as 113(45.9%) women indicated that their in-laws were used to poke nosing into their family issues, 97(39.4%) women suffered domestic violence from their spouse under the influence of alcohol/substance while 99(40.2%) women suffered domestic violence due to negative influence of bad friends on their spouse. 41(16.7%) women suffered as their spouse could not contribute financially to the welfare of the family due to lack of job (Table 3)

Table 3: Factors responsible for domestic violence against women (N= 246)

Factors responsible for domestic violence	Yes		No	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
My spouse consume alcohol/substance	97	39.4	149	60.6
Inability of my spouse to cater for the family and low financial income	54	22.0	192	78.0
Age disparity between my spouse and I causes domestic violence	49	19.9	197	80.1
My spouse has no job, so he is not contributing anything to family welfare.	41	16.7	205	83.3
Religious differences causes disagreement and fight between us	36	14.6	210	85.4
My spouse go out with bad friends who have negative influence in him	99	40.2	147	59.8
Because I have no child yet is the major problem causing quarrel between my spouse and me	41	16.7	205	83.3
The psychological and poor mental health status of my spouse is responsible for domestic violence	31	12.6	215	87.4
My in-laws are used to poke nosing into my family issues.	113	45.9	133	54.1

Qualitative Report

Table 4 depicts 2 themes and 13 sub-themes. The theme on prevalence of domestic had three sub-themes, causes of domestic violence theme had ten sub-themes.

TABLE 4: Main Themes and Subthemes Generated from Data

Theme	Main theme	Sub-themes	Participants (n=19)	
			f	Percentage
1.	Prevalence of domestic violence	Had experienced domestic violence	5	(26.3%)
		Had neither experienced domestic violence nor had dispute	4	(21.1%)
		Had not experienced domestic violence but had disputes	10	(52.6%)
2.	Causes of domestic violence	Extra marital affairs	8	(42.1%)
		Misunderstanding	12	(63.2%)
		Alcohol	4	(21.1%)
		failure to provide and care for the family	6	(31.6%)
		Pride and ego	9	(47.4%)
		Deprivation of food and sex	5	(26.3%)
		Poverty	13	(68.4%)
		No law against DV perpetrator	6	(31.6%)
		Family background	8	(42.1%)
		Mental disorder	6	(31.6%)

THEME 1: Prevalence of Domestic Violence

1) Had experienced domestic violence

This theme reported that some women experienced domestic violence and left the relationship, majority of them were assisted by their relatives to get off the hook. They all confirmed that the perpetrators were lovely and good at the initial stage of the relationship.

"Hmm... it is not good the way men are maltreating their wives because I'm one of the victim of domestic violence. Some men are so stubborn and wicked. The first man I got married to often to beat me severely on daily basis". (P17, 47years, public servant and polygamy family)

2) Had neither experienced domestic violence nor had dispute

Very few of the participants fall in this category, some of the married women interviewed claimed that they have never experienced neither domestic violence nor had misunderstanding in their relationships.

".....I don't have any problem with my marriage oooMy husband is a very gentle person, whatever I want, is what he likes, whenever I take a step, he would support me, so I am pleased with my relationship"..(P8, 50years, Trader, Monogamy)

3) Had not experienced domestic violence but had disputes

Majority agreed that they had dispute but no domestic violence was recorded. Those in this categories agreed that dispute in marriage is a normal thing and asserted that there is no perfect marriage. Others agree that in the heat of hot argument they usually withdraw to their rooms and wait for their husbands to claim down.

"Since I have gotten married my husband has never raised his hand on me ooo, he is very jovial, he provides for the family and take good care of us, he helped me to do home chores, he pays school fees on time" (P2, 33years, Trader, Monogamy)

Theme 2: Causes of Domestic Violence

1) Extramarital affairs

Almost half of the participants agreed that extra marital affair could either come from husband or wife and this is responsible for domestic violence in the society.

"...the husband may get angry and from there riff and trouble starts and from there the man may mingle with another woman that performs better in the kitchen and on bed." (P1, 50years, Trader, Monogamy).

"Some men had concubine outside which makes them to see the one at home as ugly and dirty type". (P14. 40years, Trader, Polygamy)

2) Misunderstanding

Misunderstanding was generally believed to be responsible for domestic violence, this was asserted by majority of the married women interviewed, while only few were indifferent to misunderstanding as a factor responsible for domestic violence among families. Majority agreed that marriage cannot be devoid of misunderstanding and argument but women should know when to withdraw to their rooms.

"What I think can be responsible for man maltreating , Trader, Monogamy)

3) Alcohol

Alcohol consumption was fingered by just few of the participants. Some of the perpetrators of domestic violence are drunks, after the effect of the alcohol has gone they are usually remorseful and sober for their actions. While majority did not imbibe that alcohol could make a man to inflict injury on his lovely wife.

"once the husband gets home he would bounce on her with beating but once the alcohol he drank has wear off, he may now start begins the wife "my wife please don't be offended, don't allow outsider to know about it, it's not my fault" but in my own point of view, battering wife or one's partner is very wrong". (P14. 40years, Trader, Polygamy)

4) Failure to provide and care for the family

Inability of man to provide and cater for the family was mentioned by few of the interviewees, more than half of the married women participated in the study did not agreed that this could lead to domestic violence.

"...in a situation whereby the husband fails to finance household responsibilities and such a man may come home in the evening asking for food and in the course of agreement, trouble may ensue". (P8, 50years, Trader, Monogamy).

5) Pride and Ego

The participants said these could come from either the husband or wife, although many said it is important for women to be submissive to their husband. Less than half of the married women believed that arrogance could be responsible for domestic violence in Ado Ekiti.

"..... To the best of my knowledge pride can also cause domestic violence, disrespect to in-laws is also a cause".(P13, 32years, Trader, Polygamy).

6) Deprivation of food and sex

Food and sex were seen as two things that can cause domestic violence. However, only few participants indicated that deprivation of food and sex were major causes of domestic violence which most couples do not discuss in the public.

"He may say she should be eating unripe plantain and after that he will demand for sex and the wife will not agree. He even beat....".(P2, 33years, Trader, Monogamy).

"...in a situation whereby the wife refuse or fail to prepare meal for the husband despite that the husband had made provision for feeding before leaving for work, in this, the husband may get angry and from there riff..... (P8, 50years, Trader, Monogamy)

7) Poverty

Poverty was popularly agreed to be the root cause of domestic violence, majority of the participants said that poverty was seriously responsible for frequent occurrence of domestic violence in the society. While few of the participants did not subscribe to it by saying one does not need to be rich before he or she can enjoy peaceful marriage.

"...so mostly, poverty is the major cause of domestic violence. Though some men are very stingy, they have enough but not willing to care for their home" (P11, 40years, Trader, Polygamy).

"if the husband is able to cater or shoulder the responsibilities at home, there will be no problem: for instance if I need ₦50,000 and my husband is able to provide or give me, definitely there would not be bagging or riff at home" (P12, 40years, Trader, Monogamy).

8) No law against DV perpetrators

The married women interviewed believed that if there were functional law on domestic violence this would curb incessant maltreating of women and children, only few were of opinion that lack of functional law on domestic violence could be responsible.

"What I know is that the society looks down on women as if they are nothing, some men would even say if I beat her, nothing would happen..." (P18, 35years, Trader, Monogamy)

9) Family background

The behavior of couples could be traced to their families. Many believed that couples imitate their parents, less than half of the participants said family background of the couples played major role in the stability of the marriage or whether domestic violence would be

experienced or not. Someone that experienced domestic violence at childhood is likely to also undergo domestic violence when married, this assertion was vehemently disagreed by majority of the participants.

"The type of family the man came from (background) may be that is how his father has been beating his mother (Imitation)". (P6, 35years, civil servant, Monogamy).

10) Mental disorder

A victim of domestic violence who still remain in the relationship was seen as an insane person by some of the participants, while the perpetrators of domestic violence were recommended for psychiatric test. Table 4.9 indicated that few participants declared that one of the causes of domestic violence has to do with mental status of the perpetrators. Although majority were of the opinion that mental disorder was not a cause.

"So many things can be responsible for domestic violence, some of these are idleness, unemployment, lack of home training, devil, mental disorder and illiteracy" (P15, 40years, Public servant).

Test of Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant association between socio-economic status and level of domestic violence.

Table 5: Association between socio-economic status and level of domestic violence (N = 246)

Socio-economic status	Level of domestic violence experience				Chi-Sq.	df	Pv	R
	Experienced no domestic violence at all	Experience low level domestic violence	Experience mid-level domestic violence	Experienced high level domestic violence				
High	16	16	6	8	10.02	3	0.02	S
	22.9%	30.2%	9.5%	13.3%				
Low	54	37	57	52	10.02	3	0.02	S
	77.1%	69.8%	90.5%	86.7%				

Table 5 showed participant's association between socio-economic status and level of domestic violence experienced. In the table of result, those who had low socio-demographic status constituted 77.1% while those who had high socio-demographic status constituted 22.9% of the participants. Moreover, those who had low socio-demographic status suffered domestic violence across all levels of domestic violence more than those who had high socio-demographic status. This shows that socio-economic status had a major influence on domestic violence. This was found to be statically significant (Chi-Sq = 10.02; df = 3; pv = 0.02). Therefore, the null-hypothesis 1 was rejected.

Ho2: There is no significant association between participant's level of education and level of domestic violence

Table 6: Association between participant's level of education and level of domestic violence (N = 246)

Level of education	Level of domestic violence experience				Chi-Sq.	df	pv	R
	Experienced no domestic violence at all	Experience low level domestic violence	Experience mid-level domestic violence	Experienced high level domestic violence				
No formal education/Primary	13	9	16	11	10.3	6.0	0.1	NS
	18.6%	17.0%	25.4%	18.3%				
Secondary	27	9	19	21				
	38.6%	17.0%	30.2%	35.0%				
Tertiary	30	35	28	28				
	42.9%	66.0%	44.4%	46.7%				

Result of findings from table 6 showed that participants who were in tertiary level of education suffered domestic violence more than participants in other (lesser) levels of education. Also participants in Tertiary level, Secondary level and those who had no formal/primary level of education constituted 42.9%, 38.6% and 18.6% respectively. This was found to be statically not-significant (Chi-Sq = 10.3; df = 6; pv = 0.1). Therefore, the null-hypothesis 2 was accepted (Table 6)

Ho3: There is no significant association between participant's type of family and level of domestic violence

Table 7: Association between type of family and level of domestic violence (N = 246)

Type of family	Level of domestic violence experience				Chi-Sq.	df	pv	R
	Experienced no domestic violence at all	Experience low level domestic violence	Experience mid-level domestic violence	Experienced high level domestic violence				
Monogamy	51	36	31	31	12.9	6	0.04	S
	72.9%	67.9%	49.2%	51.7%				
Polygamy	14	11	24	24				
	20.0%	20.8%	38.1%	40.0%				

Extended	5	6	8	5				
	7.1%	11.3%	12.7%	8.3%				

Findings from table 7 above showed that participants with monogamy family setting experienced domestic violence across all levels more than participants with Polygamy and extended family settings. Hence, participants in monogamy, polygamy and extended family settings constituted 72.9%, 20% and 7.1% respectively to those who did not experience domestic violence at all. This was found to be statically significant ($\chi^2 = 12.9$; $df = 6$; $p = 0.04$). Therefore, the null-hypothesis 3 was rejected (Table 7)

Discussion

The study revealed that up to 40 percent of the women claimed that they were always treated like servants by their spouse, A total of 37 percent claimed that their spouse insulted them in front of others while 63 percent claimed negative. Above a quarter of the women claimed that their spouses had slapped them times without number. A near ratio of them claimed that their spouses had pushed/shook, kicked/dragged and forced them to engage in un-natural sexual practices, which they hated. This report however tallies with findings from a study carried out in a rural area of Bangladesh during December 2000, where many women reported that they were usually beaten and physically assaulted by their husbands (Bhuiya, 2016). This also agrees with findings from a study conducted by (Hegarty, et al., 2012) which outlined a comprehensive definition of “domestic violence” also outlining examples of abusive behaviour. In addition to this, a study conducted in Nigeria on 308 Igbo women showed that 78.8% of the women have been battered by their male counterparts, out of whom 58.9% reported battering during pregnancy, and 21.3 % reported having been forced to have sexual intercourse (Agnihotri, et al, 2016). Also, more than a quarter of the women claimed that their spouses had been unfaithful to them and have had extra-marital relationships. Moreover, a similar study which was conducted on married women in urban Lahore, Pakistan showed that most women reported that they were slapped, beaten, injured and thrown out of the house by their respective husbands (Guedes et al. 2015).

On the factors responsible for domestic violence against women, the study revealed that up to 39 percent of the women claimed that their spouse consumed alcohol. Furthermore, close to a quarter of the women think that one of the factors responsible for domestic violence against women is the inability of their spouse to cater for the family and low financial income. This is similar to a study conducted on married women in urban Lahore, Pakistan. The study which aimed at finding the association between socio-economic status and domestic violence indicated that women’s socio economic status had strong bearing on their exposure to domestic violence (Guedes, 2015). Less than a quarter of the participants claimed that the age disparity between them and their spouse causes domestic violence. Less than a quarter of the women said that their spouse had no job, so he was not contributing anything to family welfare. A near ratio claimed that one of the factors responsible for domestic violence was due to the religious differences which existed between them and their spouse. However, 40 percent of the women claimed that one of the factors responsible for

domestic violence was due to the fact that their spouse go out with bad friends who have negative influence on them. Another cross section of the participants felt that the reason behind the domestic violence they are faced which could be because they had no child yet.

Conclusion

The study concludes that women are the major victims of domestic violence in our society today. All attempts to eradicate this unacceptable crime should be encouraged by all countries. The study also concludes that the proportion of domestic violence in Ekiti State was high while there was relationship between socio-economic status and level of domestic violence. Also type of family was related with the level of domestic violence. However, there was no relationship between educational level and level of domestic violence.

Recommendations

In response to the problems of domestic violence against women, the following recommendations were made by the researcher;

1. Public awareness should be created in social gatherings like churches, mosque, seminars, symposium and social media about domestic violence.
2. Counsellors in various institutions should counsel youths and couples on the ills of domestic violence, women and victims should speak out and make report to appropriate channel like law enforcement agents and gender center.
3. Women should be encouraged not to keep silent when battered or victimized, perpetrators and relatives should be involved in the care of the victims.
4. Parents and teachers should strive to infuse good moral and religious values in children and also serve as role models.

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Cite this article:

Author(s), OJO, Taiwo Folake (RN, RM, BNSc, PGDE, M.Sc.), (2021). “Prevalence, Nature and Causes of Domestic Violence in Ekiti State”, **Name of the Journal:** Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 9 –24. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6012581 , Issue: 9, Vol.: 3, Article: 2, Month: September, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

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